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Research

**EVALUATE THE COMFORT AND VIABILITY OF
SULFASALAZINE IN THE TREATMENT OF SEVERE
ALOPECIA AREATA**¹Dr Iqra Zamir, ²Dr Amna Abbas, ³Dr Maryam Naeem¹Fatima Memorial College of Medicine and Dentistry²Rashid Latif Medical College Lahore³King Edward Medical University**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To evaluate the comfort and viability of sulfasalazine in healing of severe alopecia areata.**Methods:** Our current research was led at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from November 2017 to October 2018. This was a useful non-randomized, open-ended preliminary. A total of 45 subjects were recalled for review. Patients were selected from the branch of the Dermatology Unit II of the Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. Subjects were observed with 500mg/day of sulfasalazine at a limit of 4 grams/day. The portion for the youngsters was 10mg/kg/day. Patients were followed up every two weeks. Reactive patients were followed for an additional 4 months. All important information was recorded and ventilated.**Results:** Four out of 64 patients (7%) responded to treatment. Two of these patients had a mid-reaction and two had a complete reaction. There was no significant gender contrast in the response to treatment. The significant symptom observed was the hepatotoxicity found in 5 patients resulting in suspension of the drug.**Conclusion:** Sulfasalazine is presumed to be moderately protected but not viable in the treatment of extreme AA.**Keywords:** Alopecia areata, alopecia total, alopecia universalis, sulphasalazine.**Corresponding author:****Iqra Zamir,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Alopecia areata (AA) is an immune system problem that results in irregular male pattern baldness without scarring.¹ The disease can occur at any age, but its peak frequency is in the second and third decade. The disease affects both sexes equally. The autoimmune nature of the disease is recommended by the discovery by biopsy of included territories that show transcendent T cell penetration around the hair follicles [1]. It is also linked to other immune system diseases such as vitiligo, thyroiditis, and vindictive anemia. Severe types of AA include broad AA, total alopecia (TA), and universal alopecia (UA). Broad AA is more than 41% male pattern baldness from hairy areas. Total alopecia is the total absence of hair in the terminal phase of the scalp and universal alopecia is the absolute loss of hair in the terminal phase of the body and scalp [2]. Intralesional corticosteroids are used as first-line treatment for limited summary AA. Intralesional corticosteroids are used as first-line treatment for limited summary AA. They stimulate hair regrowth at the infusion site [3]. The effect lasts for a few months and re-treatment may sometimes be necessary. The different options available for limited summary AA are intense topical corticosteroids, dithranol and minoxidil cream. These are protected, but the results of treatment are unsatisfactory. The results of treatment are not satisfactory [4]. Deliberate topical operators are used in the treatment of extreme AA. Topical operators incorporate corticosteroids, minoxidil, psoralen therapy with light irradiation (PUVA), and anthralin. The topical operators are used to treat extreme AA. Routine therapies other than oral and parenteral corticosteroids incorporate cyclosporine. The use of cyclosporine is not recommended for the treatment of extreme AA. Contact immunotherapy with diphenylcyclopropanone (DPCP) or quadratic corrosive dibutyl ester (SADBE) is also suggested for extreme cases of AA. Hair regrowth occurs in about half of cases, but the response rate is much lower in patients with TA and UA. Its limitation is that it is not generally available and involves a variety of hospital visits.⁶ Baseline corticosteroids and continuous or beating PUVA have been tried to treat severe AA. Because of the lack of demonstrated adequacy and the possibility of true symptoms, these treatments have not been prescribed to date [5]. The treatment of severe AA has not yet been proven to be effective. In general, alternatives to the treatment of extreme

AA are limited and do not provide good results. Because they primarily influence patient satisfaction, new restorative alternatives are, in this way, basic. Sulfasalazine is a mitigating agent and has been used in various immune system disorders such as rheumatoid inflammation of the joints, psoriasis, and challenging internal infection. It has immunosuppressive and immunomodulating effects. There are virtually no case reports of this drug being obtained in patients with extreme AA. Sulfasalazine, in this sense, is an alternative that should be investigated in the treatment of AA.

METHODOLOGY:

Our current research was led at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from November 2017 to October 2018. This was a useful non-randomized, open-ended preliminary. A total of 45 subjects were recalled for review. Patients were selected from the branch of the Dermatology Unit II of the Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. A total of fifty patients, meeting the criteria for consideration, were selected for review. The conclusion of the AA was made clinically. They were of both sexes, over two years of age and had the disease with the association of more than 27% of scalp territory with or without hair loss on other parts of the body. It was guaranteed that they had no particular prescription for the most recent month. Criteria for prohibition included patients with evidence of incessant organ failure, e.g., incessant kidney failure, cardiovascular failure, constant liver and lung disease, pregnant and lactating women, and those with extreme sensitivity to salvation from additional drugs and salicylates. All applicable information, including history, physical assessment and the site, size and degree of alopecia, was recorded in a pro forma. Pre-treatment investigations included a total blood count, renal capacity tests, liver capacity tests, and urinalysis. Following the underlying workup, patients over 14 years of age received a dose of 500mg/day of sulfasalazine. The dose was increased by 500 mg steadily to a limit of 43 g/day. In patients under 1 years of age, the starting dose was 10 mg/kg body weight and was increased steadily by 10 mg/kg to a limit of 70 mg/kg body weight. The most extreme portion was not required in each patient and the determinant in establishing the measurements was hair regrowth. The remainder of the treatment plan is shown in Figure 1. Patients were followed up, the first week after the week to the extent necessary to obtain a response and then every two weeks. At each visit, the above-mentioned examinations were repeated every fortnight for the first month and

at regular intervals thereafter. The reaction was examined on a scale (Table 1).

Table 1: Grades of improvement.

Grade	Recovery (%)
0	No response
1	1-25%
2	26-50%
3	51-75%
4	>75%

Figure 1: Study protocol for sulphasalazine in alopecia areata.

Table 2 Age and gender distribution of study population (n=41).

Group	Total number	Alopecia areata >25% of scalp area n (%)	Alopecia totalis n (%)	Alopecia universalis n (%)
Males	23	13 (31.7)	5 (12.2)	5 (12.2)
Females	18	12 (29.3)	3 (7.3)	3 (7.3)
Total Number	41	25 (61.0)	8 (19.5)	8 (19.5)

Table 3: The cure response to sulphasalazine in diverse kinds of alopecia areata (n=42).

Category	Number	No response	Partial response	Total response	Overall response
Extensive alopecia areata	25	24	0	1	1
Alopecia totalis	8	6	1	1	2
Alopecia universalis	8	7	1	0	1
Total number	41	37	2	2	4
P value		<0.05	>0.05	>0.05	>0.05

Evaluations 2 and 3 were viewed as incomplete reaction while grade 4 was taken as all out reaction. SPSS form 23 was applied for our research. The aspects observed were segment material and remained displayed as up-front measurements. The outcome of medication cure was assessed by hair regrowth. It was connected as either not any reaction or reaction which might be central or comprehensive. The association of reaction A p estimation of <0.06 was measured noticeably remarkable.

RESULTS:

Sixty patients were from the outset evaluated the examination. There were nine dropouts. Out of them, prescription was stopped in three patients in perspective on agitated liver limit tests. Six patients didn't turn up for advancement. Thus, study was done in 43 patients. There were 24 folks and 19 females. 62% patients were of wide AA, and 21% all of alopecia complete is and alopecia universalis. Age and sexual direction apportionment are showed up in Table 2.

Figure 2: Cure reply amongst male and womanly cases.

Sufficiency of medicine is showed up in Table 3. In expansive AA, 2 (8%) understanding showed total response; in alopecia totalis 1 out of 9 (14.7%) patients exhibited total response however sedate was unable in alopecia totalis. Concerning impacts, 5 out of 48 patients made clinical and inquire about focus verification of liver damage. Among them two were folks and one female. None of the patients made hematologic varieties from the standard. The drug was ensured at this point not solid in alopecia areata.

DISCUSSION:

Our assessment demonstrated that sulphasalazine isn't convincing in the organization of genuine alopecia areata. Regardless, our results differentiate from that of study drove by Ellis et al. in Michigan USA. This is the fundamental examination of sulphasalazine in AA coordinated all around, which showed hair regrowth in 25% cases [6]. Regardless, note that the examination relied upon five case reports in a manner of speaking. Likewise, there was no follow-up to see the apostatize. The qualification appropriately rates may be a direct result of some racial, genetic or biological components. It may similarly be a direct result of difference in

treatment routine and term of therapy [7]. Minor responses related to gastrointestinal structure were not nitty gritty in our assessment probably due to low estimations when stood out from that used in other resistant framework issue like rheumatoid joint torment and provocative entrail ailment and moreover because of use of enteric secured tablets. 8% of our patients had disturbed liver limits [8]. Note that when liver hurtfulness occurred in our examination, it did accordingly in starting two months. From this observation we derive that the response of sulphasalazine isn't partition related. It may be an impossible to miss reaction [9]. As for other treatment options for AA like steroids, topical minoxidil, anthralin, PUVA, interferon and dapsone, all have variable responses and upkeep treatment is routinely required. Sulphasalazine is subsequently another development in a broad overview of remedial administrators. It is at any rate ground-breaking in some number of patients. It will in general be an alternative as opposed to the patients who dodge the drawn out usage of jumbled experts. Differentiated and the other treatment modalities, sulphasalazine is up 'til now a desire for sheltered and wide cases that are non-responsive to various strategies for treatment [10].

CONCLUSION:

In the light of present assessment, it is proposed that sulphasalazine is connected with unsatisfactory response in patients with genuine AA. Further examinations are required to set up its reasonability especially in blend in with other treatment modalities.

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